

DEEP LEARNING-DRIVEN SEGMENTATION OF RESIN-RICH AREAS IN 3D CT IMAGING OF CFRTP-SMC

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic sheet molding compounds (CFRTP-SMCs) are gaining attention for their combination of high stiffness, formability, and lightweight characteristics. However, local heterogeneities—especially resin-rich areas formed near the edges of fiber tapes—can significantly influence mechanical and functional properties. While these regions are visually distinguishable in X-ray computed tomography (CT) images, their automated identification remains challenging due to subtle boundaries and structural complexity.

This study proposes a deep learning-based approach to automatically segment resin-rich areas in 3D X-ray CT images of CFRTP-SMCs. We first prepared composite specimens using a controlled molding process and acquired high-resolution CT scans capturing detailed internal microstructures. Since no existing methods could reliably identify resin-rich zones, we constructed a ground truth dataset via manual 3D annotation, supported by interpolation techniques. Each data sample consisted of a 3D CT image paired with a binarized label identifying resin-rich regions. We trained a 3D segmentation model using the nnU-Net framework, optimized for material imaging tasks. To enhance generalization and compensate for the limited dataset size, we applied data augmentation, intensity normalization, and cross-validation. The model architecture incorporates convolutional blocks with deep supervision to ensure stable training and accurate feature learning.

Our results demonstrate that the model accurately segmented resin-rich areas, outperforming classical texture-based methods. Crucially, it generalized well to unseen data and supported predictions on larger input volumes, confirming its robustness and scalability. This represents one of the first automated methods for 3D segmentation of resin-rich regions in CFRTP-SMCs using deep learning. The proposed framework enables more efficient and objective internal structure characterization of complex composites, opening the door to automated evaluation of local features that influence macroscopic performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic sheet molding compounds (CFRTP-SMCs) are advanced composites composed of long, discontinuous carbon fibers arranged in randomly oriented strands (ROS). These materials exhibit mechanical properties—particularly stiffness—comparable to quasi-isotropic laminates, making them well-suited for stiffness-critical structural designs. Their excellent formability also enables the production of complex, net-shaped components, expanding their applicability in industries requiring lightweight and geometrically intricate parts. In addition, CFRTP-SMCs offer favorable characteristics such as corrosion resistance and cost-efficient processing, positioning them as strong alternatives to metal components in many applications [1,2,3,4].

A notable microstructural feature of CFRTP-SMCs is the presence of resin-rich areas, typically occurring near the edges of fiber tapes. These regions are defined by a local excess of resin and a corresponding lack of fiber reinforcement. Although relatively small in size, they can substantially influence composite properties such as strength, toughness, volume resistivity, and failure strain. Monte Carlo simulations have shown that the region within approximately 2 mm of the tape edge plays a critical role in pull-out behavior, highlighting the importance of accurately identifying these resin-rich areas.

Furthermore, these regions often delineate internal boundaries, offering valuable information about the material's microstructural architecture [5,6].

While human experts can visually identify resin-rich areas in X-ray computed tomography (CT) images, automating this process is difficult due to ambiguous boundaries and structural variability. Existing methods are typically limited to indirect estimation from 2D images, are time-consuming, and lack generalizability across different composite configurations [7,8]. The structural complexity of CFRTP-SMCs presents significant challenges for traditional analysis approaches.

To address this gap, we propose a deep learning-based framework using the nnU-Net model [9] for automatic segmentation of resin-rich areas in 3D X-ray CT images. Our approach demonstrates high segmentation accuracy and strong generalization capability, even with limited training data. This work provides a foundation for comprehensive and automated internal microstructural characterization of CFRTP-SMCs.

2 METHODS

2.1 Specimen Preparation and X-ray CT Scanning

CFRTP-SMC specimens were fabricated using an automatic press molding machine (PINETTE PEI) by stacking 12 plies of carbon fiber prepregs into panels measuring $250 \times 125 \times 2$ mm. To facilitate high-resolution imaging, narrow rectangular specimens were cut to approximately $2 \times 2 \times 60$ mm, optimized for microfocus X-ray CT scanning. Imaging was conducted using a TDM 1000-IS 3D X-ray CT system (Yamato Scientific Co., Ltd.), achieving a voxel resolution sufficient to capture the detailed internal morphology, including individual fiber strands and resin distributions.

2.2 Generating Ground Truth Labels and Datasets

Automating the identification of resin-rich areas in CFRTP-SMCs is complex due to the need to detect un-reinforced pixels, consider the density of adjacent fibers, and the lack of clear boundary definitions. Currently, no existing methods can automatically segment these areas; therefore, we opted for manual labeling to generate ground truth labels.

Figure 1: Workflow for manually generating ground truth labels of resin-rich areas for training data. (Scale: $256 \times 256 \times 256$ voxels, $0.425 \times 0.425 \times 0.425$ mm³.)

Figure 1 illustrates the workflow for manually generating ground truth labels for training data. Raw X-ray CT images were uniformly cropped to dimensions of $256 \times 256 \times 256$ voxels, with each voxel measuring $1.7 \mu\text{m}$. The manual segmentation process began with the segmentation of 2D slices. Subsequently, an interpolation method was employed to automatically generate a 3D segmentation map of the resin-rich areas. The final training dataset comprised 26 pairs of 3D images of CFRTP-SMCs, with each pair consisting of a raw grayscale X-ray CT image and a corresponding binarized label image that highlighted the segmented resin-rich areas.

For dataset preprocessing, intensity normalization was applied to ensure consistency in voxel intensities across scans. Given the limited dataset size, data augmentation techniques were employed to enhance model generalization, with augmentations computed on-the-fly by CPU background workers. Additionally, a 5-fold cross-validation split was implemented to provide a robust assessment of the model's performance.

2.3 Model Training

Figure 2 illustrates the 3D U-Net architecture tailored for segmenting resin-rich areas in CFRTP-SMCs. The input patch size was set to $128 \times 128 \times 128$ voxels, cropped from the original $256 \times 256 \times 256$ image volumes. This relatively large patch size enables the network to capture broader contextual features critical for detecting subtle, spatially diffuse patterns such as resin-rich zones. To accommodate memory constraints, the batch size was limited to 2. To ensure stable training with small batches, instance normalization was used instead of batch normalization.

Figure 2: 3D U-Net network architecture for resin-rich areas segmentation.

The architecture consisted of a 3D U-Net with two convolutional blocks per resolution level in both encoder and decoder paths. Each block included a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ convolution, instance normalization, and a Leaky ReLU activation with a negative slope of 0.01. Downsampling and upsampling were performed using strided and transposed convolutions, respectively. The number of feature maps started at 32 and increased with each downsampling step, capped at 320.

Training was conducted using stochastic gradient descent with Nesterov momentum ($\mu = 0.99$) and an initial learning rate of 0.01. The learning rate followed a polynomial decay policy. The loss function combined cross-entropy and Dice loss, with deep supervision applied at multiple decoder layers. We employed a 5-fold cross-validation scheme, and each fold was trained for 100 epochs with 250 mini-batches per epoch on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 GPU.

Performance was monitored using a 'global Dice' score calculated from validation patches. Most folds demonstrated stable training and convergence. One exception was Fold 4, where validation loss fluctuated due to labeling inconsistencies in the validation set.

2.4 Inference

After training, inference was performed using a sliding window strategy with the same patch size as used during training ($128 \times 128 \times 128$ voxels). To ensure smooth and accurate predictions across the entire volume, windows were overlapped by 50% in all directions. Because segmentation accuracy tends to degrade near the patch borders, a Gaussian importance weighting scheme was applied. This approach assigns higher weights to the center voxels and reduces the influence of border regions when aggregating softmax outputs.

To further enhance prediction robustness, test-time augmentation was employed by mirroring the input images along each of the three spatial axes. Predictions from each augmented version were averaged to produce the final output.

For final segmentation, we utilized an ensemble of the five models trained during the 5-fold cross-validation. Each model was used to predict on the test set, and their outputs were combined using softmax averaging. This ensemble approach helped reduce prediction variance and improved overall segmentation accuracy. The best-performing configuration, determined by the average Dice score across training folds, was used for final inference.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Enhanced Predictions Over Manual Labeling

To evaluate the segmentation performance in more detail, Figure 3 presents three cases where the model outperforms manual labeling:

Figure 3: Three cases of the the model input (raw X-ray CT image), the corresponding manual labels of resin-rich areas, and the predicted segmentation map generated by the model. (Scale: $256 \times 256 \times 256$ voxels, $0.425 \times 0.425 \times 0.425 \text{ mm}^3$.)

Case i: A resin-rich area was missed during manual labeling (false negative), but the model successfully detected it. This highlights the model's higher sensitivity and its ability to mitigate human oversight in identifying subtle resin-rich regions.

Case ii: Manual labeling overestimated the extent of resin-rich areas (false positives), incorrectly marking non-defective regions. The model, though slightly conservative, produced more precise segmentations with fewer false positives, particularly beneficial for identifying resin-rich zones between fiber tapes.

Case iii: For irregularly shaped resin-rich areas, manual segmentation produced coarse, discontinuous boundaries due to the limitations of 2D-based interpolation. The model, leveraging 3D analysis, achieved smooth and accurate boundary delineation.

3.2 Comparison with Texture Classification

Figure 4 compares the segmentation results of our model with those produced by a classical texture-supervised classification method implemented in Avizo. While the texture method relies on local statistical features, such as variance and histogram-based descriptors, it struggles with the complex nature of resin-rich areas. The results exhibited numerous false positives, especially near the image borders.

In contrast, the deep learning model generated cleaner and more reliable segmentation outputs. This comparison underscores the advantage of learning-based methods in capturing global patterns and spatial context, which are essential for accurately segmenting heterogeneous regions in CFRTP-SMCs.

Figure 4: The comparison between the texture classification results and the segmentation of resin-rich areas generated by our model. (Scale: $256 \times 256 \times 256$ voxels, $0.425 \times 0.425 \times 0.425 \text{ mm}^3$.)

3.3 Verification with Fiber Analysis

To validate the physical relevance of the segmented resin-rich areas, we conducted a fiber orientation analysis based on geometric correlation with parametric cylinder templates. This approach enables the identification and tracing of individual carbon fibers according to their local orientation and spatial continuity. The segmented resin-rich regions consistently coincided with zones of low fiber density, confirming their characterization as fiber-deficient, resin-rich areas. Moreover, these regions frequently appeared between fiber tapes exhibiting distinct orientation patterns, indicating that the model successfully identifies resin accumulations at inter-tape boundaries. These results demonstrate that the model's predictions are not only visually consistent with expert expectations but also structurally meaningful in the context of composite microarchitecture.

3.4 Prediction on Unseen Data

To assess generalization capability, the trained model was applied to a larger, previously unseen CT image with dimensions of $600 \times 600 \times 600$ voxels—over 12 times the size of the training patches. As shown in Figure 5, the model successfully segmented resin-rich areas across multiple planes (xy , yz , xz) and in the full 3D volume.

Figure 5: Prediction of resin-rich areas on unseen data. The green hatched regions indicate the model's prediction of resin-rich areas. (Scale: $600 \times 600 \times 600$ voxels, $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$.)

The predicted regions aligned well with visually identifiable resin-rich zones, confirming that the model generalizes effectively beyond the training distribution. This robustness is particularly valuable for real-world applications involving full-scale parts, where input dimensions vary and high-resolution analysis of internal structures is critical.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of the nnU-Net deep learning framework in automatically segmenting resin-rich areas in 3D X-ray CT images of CFRTP-SMCs. The results reveal several key advantages and implications of the proposed approach:

First, the model successfully automates the segmentation process, reducing reliance on manual labeling and improving both efficiency and consistency. It consistently produces smoother and more accurate boundary delineations than conventional 2D-based manual methods, effectively addressing interpolation artifacts and labeling noise. Moreover, its robust 3D analysis enables accurate segmentation of irregularly shaped resin-rich regions—an area where traditional techniques often fall short.

Second, compared to conventional texture-based classification methods, the nnU-Net model achieves significantly higher segmentation accuracy. While texture-based approaches are limited by local feature dependence and prone to false positives, the deep learning model captures complex structural patterns with superior generalization.

Third, the physical relevance of the predicted resin-rich areas was confirmed through fiber orientation analysis. The model's segmented regions consistently aligned with low fiber density zones and inter-tape boundaries, verifying their structural validity within the composite microarchitecture.

Finally, the model demonstrated strong scalability by accurately predicting resin-rich areas in large, previously unseen CT volumes. This highlights its robustness and practical applicability for high-resolution material characterization at various scales.

In summary, the nnU-Net model provides a reliable, accurate, and scalable solution for segmenting resin-rich areas in CFRTP-SMCs. Its integration into composite materials research holds promise for improving internal structure analysis, enabling advanced material characterization, and supporting automated quality control and performance evaluation.

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